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Changes in Alveolar and Cisternal Compartments Induced by Milking Interval in the Udder of Dairy Ewes

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ABSTRACT

14 The aim of this work was to evaluate the effects of milking interval (4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24
15 h) on cisternal size and milk partitioning (cisternal and alveolar) in the udders of dairy ewes.
16 Twenty-four dairy ewes (Manchega, n = 12; and Lacaune, n = 12) were used in a 2-wk
17 experiment during mid-lactation. Cisternal and alveolar milk yields were measured and milk
18 samples from each udder fraction were collected for analysis. Cisternal milk was obtained
19 after i.v. injection of an oxytocin receptor antagonist, and alveolar milk was obtained after i.v.
20 injection of oxytocin. Enlargement of cisternal compartment due to milking intervals was
21 measured by ultrasonography for each half udder. Volumes of cisternal and alveolar milk
22 differed according to breed, being greater in Lacaune (888 ± 43 mL and 338 ± 25 mL,
23 respectively) than in Manchega ewes (316 ± 43 mL and 218 ± 25 mL, respectively). Alveolar
24 milk increased linearly to 16 h in Manchega and 20 h in Lacaune, and remained constant
25 thereafter. Cisternal milk accumulated linearly to 24 h milking intervals in both breeds.
26 Cisternal area (values per udder half) increased as milking interval increased, reaching a
27 plateau at 20 h in Manchega (21 ± 1 cm²) and 16 h in Lacaune (37 ± 1 cm²). Correlation between
28 cisternal area and cisternal milk was the highest at 8 h (Manchega: $r = 0.70$ and Lacaune: $r =$
29 0.56). Cisternal area correlated with total milk ($r = 0.80$). Milk fat content varied markedly
30 with milking intervals, increasing in alveolar milk (until 12 h in Manchega, $8.90 \pm 0.18\%$; and
31 20 h in Lacaune, $8.67 \pm 0.19\%$) and decreasing until 24 h in cisternal milk ($5.74 \pm 0.29\%$ and
32 $4.85 \pm 0.29\%$, respectively). Milk protein content increased in alveolar milk until 24 h
33 (Manchega, $6.46 \pm 0.11\%$; Lacaune, $5.95 \pm 0.11\%$) but did not vary in cisternal milk. Milk
34 lactose content only decreased at the 24-h milking interval in the cisternal milk of Manchega
35 ewes ($4.60 \pm 0.04\%$). In conclusion, our results suggest that cisterns play an important role in
36 accommodating secreted milk during extended milking intervals. Thus, long milking intervals
37 could be a recommendable strategy for large-cisterned dairy sheep. Evidence suggests that
38 ultrasonography provides accurate estimations of udder cistern size and could be used as an
39 indicator for selecting large-cisterned dairy ewes.

40 (**Keywords:** ultrasonography, milking frequency, cisternal milk, dairy sheep)

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INTRODUCTION

43 Secreted milk in dairy ruminants is stored extracellularly within 2 anatomical udder
44 compartments: alveolar (alveolar lumen and small ducts) and cisternal (large ducts and gland

45 and teat cisterns). Milk partitioning between both compartments varies according to species,
46 breed, age, stage of lactation and milking interval (Bruckmaier et al., 1997; Davis et al., 1998;
47 Salama et al., 2004), and helps explain the change of milk yield and milk composition that
48 occurs when milking interval is extended to 24 h. Milk yield and milk composition changes
49 for each compartment at different milking intervals were reported by McKusick et al. (2002)
50 in dairy ewes. Cows and goats that store larger proportions of milk in the gland cistern
51 produce more milk, and are more able to tolerate extended milking intervals than those that
52 store larger proportion of milk in the alveolar compartment (Davis et al., 1998; Salama et al.,
53 2004). Dewhurst and Knight (1994) indicate that cows with small cisterns had a greater
54 response when milking frequency increased from twice- to thrice-daily milking. Moreover,
55 stripping can be suppressed in large-cisterned ewes with few effects on milk yield and a
56 dramatic reduction in milking time (Labussière et al., 1988).

57 Ultrasonography allows the non-invasive exploration of the internal structure of the
58 mammary gland and was used for measuring cisternal size in ewes (Bruckmaier and Blum,
59 1992; Ruberte et al., 1994; Nudda et al., 2000), goats (Bruckmaier and Blum, 1992; Salama et
60 al., 2004), cows (Bruckmaier and Blum, 1992; Ayadi et al., 2003). Several studies have
61 shown that ultrasonography could be useful for studying the udder changes which occur in
62 order to accommodate milk during different milking intervals and after milk letdown in cows
63 (Ayadi et al., 2003, Caja et al., 2004) and goats (Salama et al., 2004). But, as far as we know
64 ultrasonography has not been used to evaluate cisternal size changes when different milking
65 intervals are performed in dairy ewes.

66 The main objective was to study the effect of milking intervals on cisternal size and milk
67 partitioning in the udder of 2 dairy ewe breeds (Manchega and Lacaune) differing in
68 lactational performance. Composition of milk obtained from each udder compartment was
69 evaluated at different milking intervals. The experiment allowed validation of the udder

70 scanning methodology in ewes of different cistern sizes and at different intervals after
71 milking.

72 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

73 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
74 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
75 Barcelona (reference CEEAH 02/410).

76 *Animals and Management Conditions*

77 A total of 24 adult lactating dairy ewes of 2 breeds (Manchega, $n = 12$, 70.2 ± 2.4 kg BW;
78 and, Lacaune, $n = 12$, 75.5 ± 2.2 kg BW) with symmetrical and healthy udders (SCC, 64 ± 48
79 $\times 10^3$ cells/mL; <5 cfu/mL), from the experimental farm of SIGCE (Servei de Granges i
80 Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona in Bellaterra (Spain) were
81 used in a short-term experiment performed at wk 11 and 16 of lactation.

82 Ewes had similar stage of lactation (70 ± 3 DIM) and milk yield by breed (Manchega, 1.11
83 ± 0.09 L/d; and, Lacaune, 2.32 ± 0.11 L/d) in the week previous (wk 10) to the start of the
84 experiment. Ewes were allocated at wk 10 and 15 of lactation into 6 groups of 4 ewes each
85 (Manchega, $n = 2$, and Lacaune, $n = 2$), and were housed indoors, fed a dehydrated forage
86 based diet and managed as described previously by Castillo et al. (2008).

87 Ewes were milked in a double-12 stall parallel milking parlor (Westfalia Surge Ibérica,
88 Granollers, Spain), set to 42 kPa, 120 pulses/min, and 50% pulsation ratio, and equipped with
89 recording jars and low milk pipeline. Before the experiment, animals were milked twice daily
90 (0800 and 1800 h) and the milking included machine milking (without udder preparation or
91 teat cleaning), machine stripping, and teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-ioshield, Ecolab
92 Hispano-Portuguesa, Barcelona, Spain).

93 *Experimental Procedure*

94 The experiment consisted of a crossover with 6 milking intervals (4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24
95 h) at random, replicated at wk 11 and 16 of lactation. Milking interval schedule during each
96 experimental week was applied successively (total length 84 h) without any period of
97 washing-out between milking intervals. Carryover effects between milking intervals were
98 reduced by randomizing milking order of ewe groups and by removing alveolar milk at milk
99 fractions collection (Castillo et al., 2008). The experiment started (0 h) after the complete
100 udder emptying by machine milking with the help of an i.v. injection of oxytocin (2 IU/ewe;
101 Veterin Lobulor, Laboratorios Andreu, Barcelona, Spain) to remove residual milk. Thereafter,
102 one of the 6 milking interval treatments was randomly applied, and the same udder emptying
103 procedure was repeated for each milking interval treatment.

104 ***Scanning Methodology***

105 To prevent undesired milk letdown during scanning and to enable recording of cisternal and
106 alveolar milk fractions separately, each ewe was injected i.v. with 0.8 mg/ewe of atosiban, an
107 oxytocin receptor blocking agent (Tractocile 7.5 mg/mL, Ferring, Spain), while in its pen
108 before being taken to the milking parlor. Cisternal size was evaluated for each half udder by
109 measuring cisternal area by ultrasonography. Ultrasonography was conducted using a real
110 time B-mode ultrasonograph (Ultra Scan 900, Ami Medical Alliance Inc., Montreal, Canada)
111 equipped with a 5-MHz sectorial probe (2 dB power, 80° scanning angle, 0.5 mm axial and
112 1.5 mm lateral resolution). Exploration depth was 14 cm. The probe was placed directly
113 against the upper part of the medium suspensory ligament, caudally to the udder, and between
114 the inguinal lymph nodes (Ruberte et al., 1994; Rovai, 2001) using the teat as scan axis.
115 Contact gel (Geleco, Laboratorios Carreras, Barcelona, Spain) was applied to udder skin to
116 exclude air between probe and udder. Scans were done for each udder half and transferred to a
117 personal computer for image analysis. Cisternal area was calculated in triplicate for each scan

118 using image treatment software (MIP4 Advanced System, Microm España, Barcelona, Spain).
119 Area in pixels was converted to cm^2 using a conversion rate of 1,024 pixels/ cm^2 .

120 As the calculated half-life of atosiban is approximately 18 min (Wellnitz et al., 1999), a
121 single dose was sufficient to prevent milk letdown during the time that ewes were being
122 moved to the milking parlor (approximately 4 min), having scans performed on both half
123 udders (approximately 5 min) and having cisternal milk evacuated by machine milking (<2
124 min). Approximately 20 min after the atosiban injection, ewes were injected i.v. with 2 IU of
125 oxytocin and machine-milked to obtain letdown alveolar milk.

126 *Sampling and Analyses*

127 Milk volume was recorded and sampled for each milking and udder fraction. Samples of
128 approximately 100 mL were preserved with potassium dichromate (0.3 g/L) at 4°C until
129 analysis of milk composition. Unhomogenized milk samples were analyzed with a near
130 infrared spectrometer (Technicon InfraAlyzer-450, Bran+Luebbe, Nordersted, Germany) for
131 content of total solids, fat, crude protein ($\text{N} \times 6.38$), true protein, casein, and lactose. Samples
132 for SCC were preserved with an anti-microbial tablet (Bronopol, Broad Spectrum Micro-tabs
133 II, D&F Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) and kept at 4°C until analysis. The SCC was
134 determined in the DHI Laboratory of Catalonia (Allic, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain) using an
135 automatic cell counter (Fossomatic 5000, Foss Electric, Hillerød, Denmark) specifically
136 calibrated for sheep milk.

137 *Statistical Analysis*

138 Results were analyzed by the PROC MIXED procedure for repeated measurements of SAS
139 (version 8.2). The mixed model used included: the fixed effects of milking interval (4, 8, 12,
140 16, 20, and 24 h), breed (Manchega and Lacaune), milk fraction (cisternal and alveolar),
141 group (1 to 6), period (wk 11 and 16), and order of treatment application (1st to 6th); the
142 random effect of animal nested within group and breed; the interactions breed by milking

143 interval, milk fraction by milking interval, period by milking interval, breed by milk fraction,
144 and period by milk fraction; and the residual error. Differences between least squares means
145 were determined with the PDIFF test of SAS and significance was declared at $P < 0.05$.
146 Pearson's correlation coefficients between measurements were calculated. Significance was
147 declared as $P < 0.05$ unless otherwise indicated.

148 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

149 *Milk Volumes and Milk Partitioning in the Udder*

150 Volumes of cisternal and alveolar milk were greater ($P < 0.001$) in Lacaune compared to
151 Manchega ewes being the mean values across all intervals (Lacaune vs. Manchega): cisternal
152 milk, 888 vs. 316 mL (SEM, 60 mL); and, alveolar milk, 338 vs. 218 mL (SEM, 36 mL),
153 respectively. Experimental period affected ($P < 0.001$) volumes of cisternal and alveolar milk
154 in both breeds, being greater ($P < 0.05$) in the first period (wk 11) than in the second (wk 16).
155 Mean values for cisternal milk (680 vs. 525 mL; SEM, 24 mL) and alveolar milk (300 vs. 256
156 mL; SEM, 13 mL) decreased 23 and 15%, respectively.

157 Volumes of cisternal and alveolar milk varied ($P < 0.001$) according to milking interval
158 (Figure 1). Cisternal milk increased ($P < 0.05$) linearly until 24 h of udder filling (Figure 1a)
159 in both breeds. Alveolar milk increased linearly ($P < 0.05$) until 16 h in Manchega and 20 h in
160 Lacaune dairy ewes (Figure 1b). Thus, alveolar compartment saturated earlier than cisternal
161 compartment in both breeds. These results agree with the pattern of milk accumulation for
162 extended milking intervals in dairy ewes (McKusick et al., 2002) and in dairy goats (Salama
163 et al., 2004) whose alveolar milk reached plateaus 20 and 16 h after milking, respectively.
164 These authors reported that cisternal milk increased continuously until 24 h, both in ewes and
165 in goats.

166 Accumulation pattern of cisternal and alveolar milk volumes during the 4 to 24-h milking
167 interval was studied through regression analysis. The best determination coefficients were

168 obtained for linear regression, the equations (y, mL of milk fraction; x, h of milking interval;
169 $P < 0.001$) being:

170 Cisternal milk (mL):

171 Manchega ($R^2 = 0.98$), $y = 23.2 x$

172 Lacaune ($R^2 = 0.99$), $y = 64.5 x$

173 Alveolar milk (mL):

174 Manchega ($R^2 = 0.97$), $y = 92 + 9.0 x$

175 Lacaune ($R^2 = 0.99$), $y = 153 + 13.2 x$

176 The analysis of the regression lines showed that the dose of oxytocin administered was not
177 enough to completely evacuate the alveolar compartment. Volume of milk left in the
178 compartment, 66% greater in Lacaune than Manchega, agreed with the expected size of the
179 alveoli population in each breed. Lollivier and Marnet (2005) showed differences between
180 cows in the dose necessary to induce milk ejection (0.25 to 4 IU), but the doses used by these
181 authors were markedly lower (0.005 to 0.008 UI/kg BW, for a 500 kg BW cow) than in our
182 case. Thus, dose of oxytocin used (2 IU/ewe) was considered as supraphysiological for both
183 breeds (0.029 IU/kg BW, for a 70 kg BW ewe) and did not limit the contractive response of
184 the alveoli. Differences in udder morphology between the two breeds, Lacaune having larger
185 and baggier udders than Manchega (Rovai, 2001), may explain the differences observed in the
186 volume of milk left when measuring the alveolar milk fraction.

187 As expected, cisternal milk percentages were different ($P < 0.01$) between breeds. The
188 contribution of cisternal milk to total milk in the udder represented 53 and 68% in Manchega
189 and Lacaune ewes, respectively. Values were higher in Lacaune (47 to 77%) than in
190 Manchega (33 to 65%) throughout milking intervals (4 to 24 h). Percentages of cisternal milk
191 obtained in Manchega ewes were similar to McKusick et al. (2002) in East Friesian crossbred
192 dairy ewes (32 to 57%) for a similar milking interval range (4 to 24 h). On the other hand,

193 percentage of cisternal milk in Lacaune ewes was high and close to that observed in Sarda
194 ewes (82%) for a 24-h milking interval (Nudda et al., 2000). Moreover, the Sarda value may
195 have been overestimated because the authors used adrenaline instead of atosiban to avoid
196 spontaneous milk letdown.

197 With these differences in mind, dairy sheep breeds could be classified according to their
198 udder cistern features: the large-cisterned ewes, usually selected for high milk yield, present a
199 great capacity of milk storage in the cisternal compartment (e.g., Awassi, Lacaune and Sarda),
200 and the medium-cisterned ewes, which have been selected as dual-purpose or local breeds,
201 show a medium capacity for storing milk inside the cisterns (e.g., East Friesian crossbred and
202 Manchega; Labussière, 1988). Small-cisterned ewe breeds usually correspond to unselected or
203 non-dairy sheep.

204 Percentages of cisternal milk obtained for dairy ewes (Figure 1a, dotted lines) were greater
205 than values reported in Ripollesa meat sheep (24% at 4 h; Caja et al., 1999), but close to
206 Murciano-Granadina goats (75% to 24 h; Salama et al., 2004). Consequently, efficient udder
207 stimulation in dairy sheep does not seem to be a key to maximizing machine-milking fraction
208 and minimizing stripping fraction during milking.

209 Percentages of cisternal milk increased ($P < 0.05$) with time after milking and reached the
210 maximum at 24 h, although values did not differ from 16 to 20 h in Manchega and from 12 to
211 24 h in Lacaune ewes (Figure 1a). A similar evolution pattern of cisternal milk percentage
212 with increasing milking interval was found by McKusick et al. (2002) in East Friesian
213 crossbred ewes, which had the maximum percentage of cisternal milk at 24 h but did not
214 show differences between 12 and 20 h of udder filling. Experiments in dairy goats (Salama et
215 al., 2004) showed that the ability to tolerate extended milking intervals was related to the size
216 of cisternal compartment. Thus, animals that store a larger proportion of milk in the gland
217 cistern were able to tolerate extended milking intervals better than those that stored a

218 relatively larger proportion in the alveolar compartment. In our experiment, higher
219 percentages of cisternal milk were detected in Lacaune than in Manchega (Figure 1a), so
220 smaller milk losses were expected in Lacaune than in Manchega ewes when once daily
221 milking is performed. Nudda et al. (2002) reported moderate milk yield losses in Awasi
222 (18%) and Sarda (24%) ewes when a 24-h milking interval was applied for only 4 d in mid
223 lactation. Salama et al. (2003) reported an 18% milk yield loss in dairy goats milked once
224 daily throughout lactation. Studies on the long-term effect of once-daily milking have been
225 inadequate in dairy ewes, so further research is necessary to support the hypothesis of
226 applying long-term reduced milking frequencies (e.g., once daily milking) in large-cisterned
227 dairy ewes.

228 Transfer of milk from the alveoli to the cistern seemed to start really soon after milking
229 (Figure 1), without requiring that the alveolar compartment reach a saturation stage, which is
230 consistent with early observations in dairy ewes (McKusick et al., 2002) and dairy goats
231 (Salama et al., 2004). In our results, milk transfer from alveolar tissue to cistern according to
232 time after milking, appeared to occur in different manners by breed. From the 4-h milking
233 interval, Manchega and Lacaune ewes differed ($P < 0.05$) in cisternal (57 vs. 161 mL,
234 respectively; SEM, 53 mL) and alveolar (98 vs. 182 mL, respectively; SEM, 38 mL) milk
235 compartments, and the differences were maintained until 24 h (Figure 1a). Values of
236 cisternal:alveolar ratio at 24-h milking interval were 2.0:1 and 3.4:1, for Manchega and
237 Lacaune ewes, respectively. McKusick et al. (2002) reported values in East Friesian crossbred
238 ewes that were greater for alveolar milk at 4 h milking interval, supporting a large and baggy
239 udder, although cisternal:alveolar ratio at 24-h were lower (1.4:1) than in our results. These
240 results confirm the importance of the cisternal compartment in accommodating milk storage
241 when the milking interval is extended in dairy ewes, allowing significant increments of total
242 milk yield until 24-h of udder filling

243 *Cisternal Scans*

244 During ultrasonography, milk in the gland cistern was evident in the scans (Figure 2) as a
245 dark area (anechogenic) and the glandular parenchyma as a gray-white area (echogenic), in
246 agreement with other works carried out in ewes, goats, and cows (Bruckmaier and Blum,
247 1992; Ruberte et al., 1994). No differences were detected between left and right half udder
248 cisternal areas in the dairy ewes ($23.18 \pm 0.74 \text{ cm}^2$), probably because experimental ewes
249 were selected on the basis of udder symmetry, and machine milking may have contributed to
250 the udder symmetry maintenance. Therefore, left and right udder half values were averaged
251 and discussed jointly.

252 Manchega and Lacaune ewes differed significantly ($P < 0.001$) in cistern area values
253 (Figure 3). Cistern area value for Manchega ewes was 52% lower ($P < 0.001$) than for
254 Lacaune ewes (mean of all the milking intervals; Manchega: $15.01 \pm 1.00 \text{ cm}^2$ and Lacaune:
255 $31.36 \pm 1.00 \text{ cm}^2$). Other values of cisternal area in sheep are those obtained in East Friesian
256 (Bruckmaier and Blum, 1992; Bruckmaier et al., 1997; 19 to 40 cm^2), Sarda (Nudda et al.,
257 2000; 19 cm^2), Lacaune (Bruckmaier et al., 1997; 33 cm^2) and Ripollesa (Caja et al., 1999;
258 5.6 cm^2). Differences in sheep breed, stage of lactation, and hours of udder filling could
259 explain the large variability among the studies cited. Our results confirm the importance of
260 the cisternal compartment in dairy ewes (Manchega: 4 to 21 cm^2 and Lacaune: 16 to 38 cm^2 ,
261 for 4- and 24-h interval, respectively), especially in Lacaune ewes which presented cisternal
262 areas greater than those of Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (9 to 28 cm^2 for 8- and 24-h
263 interval; Salama et al., 2004).

264 Values and changes in cisternal area were affected ($P < 0.001$) by milking intervals (Figure
265 3). Cisternal areas showed curvilinear increases with milking interval, reaching a plateau at 20
266 h. These plateaus could be controversial because the cisternal milk volume increased linearly
267 up to 24-h interval in both breeds. We hypothesize that, either the frequency probe used (5

268 MHz) or the exploration depth (14 cm) were not optimum for visualizing the full extent of the
269 cisternal-cross section in the scan at extended milking intervals.

270 *Relationship between Cisternal Area and Milk Fractions*

271 Correlations between cisternal area, and cisternal, alveolar and total milk were calculated
272 for all the milking intervals tested (Table 1). Manchega and Lacaune ewes presented the
273 highest correlations between cisternal area and cisternal milk at 8-h interval (Manchega, $r =$
274 0.70 , $P < 0.001$; and Lacaune, $r = 0.56$, $P < 0.05$), which were similar to those reported by
275 Rovai (2001) in the same breeds (Manchega, $r = 0.89$; and Lacaune, $r = 0.57$) and to those
276 reported in dairy goats ($r = 0.72$ at 8 h; Salama et al., 2004), but lower than correlations
277 reported in meat sheep ($r = 0.90$ at 4 h; Caja et al., 1999).

278 In Manchega ewes, cisternal area positively correlated with volume of cisternal milk at all
279 the milking intervals ($r = 0.47$ to 0.70 ; $P < 0.05$), while in Lacaune ewes correlation was only
280 significant at the 8-h interval ($r = 0.56$, $P < 0.05$). The greater cisternal volumes presented by
281 Lacaune ewes and the use of a 5 MHz sectorial probe, with only 14 cm of exploration depth,
282 could be the cause of the low correlations observed in this breed when extended milking
283 intervals were applied. Nudda et al. (2000) reported a correlation ($r = 0.82$; 24 h after milking)
284 in large-cisterned Sarda dairy ewes using a 3.5 MHz linear probe, which gives a deeper and
285 wider exploration field and allowed better correlations at the longer milking intervals.

286 Correlation coefficients between cisternal area and total milk yield varied according to
287 breed and were less in Lacaune than in Manchega ewes (Table 1). Values in Manchega
288 ranged between 0.48 and 0.76, indicating that udder cistern size was related to the amount of
289 milk produced, and that ultrasonography could be used to identify high yielding animals in
290 this breed. In Lacaune ewes, correlation coefficients were only significant at the 8-h interval
291 ($r = 0.68$; $P < 0.01$), showing the methodological problem indicated above with regard to
292 probe depth. In both breeds, volumes of milk fractions (cisternal and alveolar) correlated with

293 total milk yield in all the milking intervals (Manchega, $r = 0.41$ to 0.93 ; Lacaune, $r = 0.50$ to
294 0.90 ; Table 1).

295 ***Composition of Milk Fractions***

296 Percentage of fat in cisternal and alveolar fractions varied inversely at different milking
297 intervals (Figure 4a). Fat content of milk fractions was affected by breed ($P < 0.001$), and was
298 always greater in Manchega than in Lacaune ewes. Fat percentage in cisternal milk
299 dramatically decreased ($P < 0.05$) as milking interval increased (Manchega, -30% ; Lacaune,
300 -36% ; between 4- and 24-h milking intervals). Conversely, milk fat content in alveolar milk
301 increased ($P < 0.05$) as milking interval increased, but reached a plateau at 12 h of udder
302 filling in Manchega (8.9% on average) and at 20 h in Lacaune (8.7% on average). The data
303 confirm that transfer of milk fat from the alveoli to the cistern slowed with the increased in
304 milking interval, producing a back-up of milk fat in the alveolar compartment, as previously
305 described in ewes (McKusick et al., 2002). Fat content in alveolar milk was higher ($P < 0.05$)
306 than percentage of fat in cisternal milk for most milking intervals studied (Manchega, 8.55 to
307 9.16% vs. 8.24 to 5.74 %; and, Lacaune, 7.26 to 8.93% vs. 7.54 to 4.84%, respectively),
308 except for the 4-h interval. The large size of fat globules, in conjunction with the active
309 expulsion required for their drainage to the cistern, favored their accumulation in the alveolar
310 compartment. Thus, milk fat concentration was usually lower in cisternal than in alveolar
311 milk in dairy ewes (Labussière, 1969; Rovai, 2001).

312 Milk protein and lactose contents were slightly affected by milking interval (Figure 4b and
313 4c). Milk protein content was greater ($P < 0.001$) in Manchega than in Lacaune ewes in both
314 cisternal ($6.10 \pm 0.09\%$ vs. $5.57 \pm 0.09\%$, respectively) and alveolar milk ($6.47 \pm 0.08\%$ vs.
315 $5.82 \pm 0.08\%$, respectively) fractions. As milking interval increased, cisternal milk fraction
316 did not modify its protein content (Manchega, $6.10 \pm 0.10\%$; Lacaune, $5.57 \pm 0.09\%$), but
317 protein content did increase in alveolar milk, remaining constant after the 12-h interval

318 (Manchega, $6.56 \pm 0.11\%$; Lacaune, $5.83 \pm 0.11\%$). No significant differences were observed
319 between milk protein percentage of cisternal and alveolar milk (Manchega: 6.10 vs. 6.47%,
320 SEM, 0.09; Lacaune: 5.57 vs. 5.82%, SEM, 0.09; $P > 0.05$; respectively), which may be
321 because milk protein is found primarily in the form of small casein micelles (Cowie and
322 Tindal, 1971) within the aqueous fraction of milk. Thus, proteins pass freely from the alveolar
323 to the cistern compartment without being as dependent on milk ejection reflex as fat content
324 is. Nevertheless, at some milking intervals, we found a small increment of protein content in
325 the alveolar fraction compared to the cisternal fraction. McKusick et al. (2002) observed
326 differences of milk protein percentages between cisternal and alveolar fractions in East
327 Friesian crossbred ewes, but only at the 24-h interval.

328 With respect to milk lactose, milking interval and breed did not affect lactose content either
329 in alveolar or in cisternal milk, except at the 24-h interval, when a significant difference
330 between cisternal and alveolar milk (4.20 vs. 4.79%, $P < 0.001$; respectively) was observed
331 only in Manchega ewes, indicating that Manchega ewes should suffer greater milk yield
332 losses than Lacaune ewes at the 24-h milking interval. Decreased lactose percentage
333 associated with longer milking intervals may be due to leaky tight junctions between
334 mammary epithelial cells. When mammary tight junctions were disrupted, the small lactose
335 molecules passed freely from milk to blood (Stelwagen et al., 1994) and the influx of
336 interstitial fluid into the milk occurred (Stelwagen et al., 1997). Both events probably favored
337 important changes in milk osmosis, provoking the decrease of lactose content observed in
338 cisternal milk of Manchega ewes. Lactose content in alveolar milk did not vary according to
339 milking interval and breed. Content of total solids showed a similar trend to milk fat content
340 (data not shown).

341 Intramammary infections were not observed during the experiment. Both breeds showed
342 low SCC in alveolar (131×10^3 cells/ml, $P = 0.74$) and cisternal milk fractions (110×10^3

343 cells/ml, $P = 0.46$). Moreover, milking interval had no effect ($P > 0.10$) on SCC in either
344 breed. Regardless of milk fractions, SCC content was similar between cisternal and alveolar
345 milk when 4, 8 and 12-h intervals were performed. Yet, alveolar milk had a greater SCC ($P <$
346 0.05) at 20 and 24 h (Figure 5). Similar results were obtained in milk fractions of East
347 Friesian crossbred ewes (McKusick et al., 2002). Taking into account that the impairment of
348 tight junctions starts from 20 h of udder filling in dairy ewes (Castillo et al., 2008), tight
349 junction disruption might have facilitated a paracellular influx of somatic cells into milk
350 (Stelwagen and Lacy-Hulbert, 1996), provoking the differences observed between cisternal
351 and alveolar milk fractions from 20 h after milking.

352

CONCLUSIONS

353 Medium and high yielding dairy ewes, such as Manchega and Lacaune, were able to adapt
354 to extended milking interval by increasing the milk volume stored in their cisternal
355 compartment. Both breeds were capable of storing large amounts of milk within the cisterns
356 and presented a pattern of milk distribution similar to dairy goats. Nevertheless, differences in
357 milk fractioning and cisternal size were detected between the 2 breeds. High yielding Lacaune
358 ewes presented greater cisternal milk percentages, higher cisternal areas, and were able to
359 store larger volumes of cisternal milk than the medium yielding Manchega ewes, suggesting
360 an easier adaptation of large-cisterned Lacaune ewes to lower milking frequencies. On the
361 other hand, ultrasonography was useful for evaluating changes in cisternal milk according to
362 time after milking and for identifying large-cisterned ewes. In both breeds, the 8-h milking
363 interval provided a more consistent estimation of the udder cistern size by ultrasonography, so
364 this interval is proposed when an estimation of the udder cistern size is desired in dairy ewes.

365

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370

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437

438 **Table 1.** Correlations between cisternal area and different milk fractions in Manchega (above
 439 diagonal) and Lacaune (below diagonal) dairy ewes milked at 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 h of
 440 milking interval.

	Milking interval	Cisternal area	Cisternal milk	Alveolar milk	Total milk
Cisternal area	4		0.56***	-	0.61***
	8		0.70***	-	0.48**
	12		0.60***	-	0.60***
	16		0.64***	0.58***	0.76***
	20		0.47**	0.53***	0.66***
	24		0.62***	0.57***	0.71***
Cisternal milk	4	-		-	0.83***
	8	0.56**		-	0.92***
	12	-		-	0.87***
	16	-		-	0.89***
	20	-		-	0.88***
	24	-		-	0.93***
Alveolar milk	4	0.51**	-		0.64***
	8	0.50**	-		0.70***
	12	-	-		0.41**
	16	-	-		0.70***
	20	-	-		0.45**
	24	-	-		0.68***
Total milk	4	-	-	0.69***	
	8	0.68***	0.83***	0.71***	
	12	-	0.83***	-	
	16	-	0.89***	0.72***	
	20	-	0.83***	0.50**	
	24	-	0.90***	-	

441 ** $P < 0.05$
 442 *** $P < 0.01$

443

444

445

446 **Figure 1.** Changes in volumes of (a) cisternal milk, and (b) alveolar milk in Manchega (○)
447 and Lacaune (□) ewes at different milking intervals. Percentages of cisternal milk of total
448 milk in the udder of Manchega (--○--) and Lacaune (--□--) ewes are shown as dotted lines.
449 Values are least squares means. Vertical bars represent SEM. ^{a-f} Means within the same breed
450 with different letters differ at $P < 0.05$.

451

452 **Figure 2.** Cisternal scans of the left half cistern of a Manchega (top line) and a Lacaune
453 (bottom line) ewes at different milking intervals. Udder cisterns filled with milk appear as
454 dark areas and the glandular parenchyma as gray-white areas.

455

456 **Figure 3.** Changes in cisternal area of mammary udder measured by ultrasonography in
457 Manchega (○) and Lacaune (□) ewes at different milking intervals. Values are least squares
458 means of half udders. Vertical bars represent SEM. ^{a-e} Means within the same breed with
459 different letters differ at $P < 0.05$.

460

461 **Figure 4.** Changes in (a) fat, (b) protein, and (c) lactose contents for cisternal (in white) and
462 alveolar (in black) milk fractions for different milking intervals in Manchega (○, ●) and
463 Lacaune (□, ■) dairy ewes. Values are least squares means. Significant differences between
464 alveolar and cisternal fractions within a time category are indicated by * ($P < 0.05$). Vertical
465 bars represent SEM. ^{a-e} Means within the same breed with different letters differ at $P < 0.05$.

466

467 **Figure 5.** Changes in SCC within cisternal (□) and alveolar (■) milk at different milking
468 intervals. Values are least squares means of Manchega and Lacaune ewes. Significant
469 differences between alveolar and cisternal fractions within a time category are indicated by *
470 ($P < 0.05$). Vertical bars represent SEM.

471

472 **Figure 1**

474 **Figure 2**

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486 **Figure 3**

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493 **Figure 5**

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